

Strengthening Bonds of Friendship between Sino-Pakistan through Chinese Author's Translated Work Published in Pakistan's National Language (Urdu)

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Abstract

The demonstration and leading role of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor are axiomatic, and the political, economic, and cultural exchanges between China and Pakistan have been further strengthened. The two sides' positions in each other's diplomatic strategy have become more prominent, and the relationship between Pakistan and China has become a model for state-to-state relations in the world. The cooperation between the two countries in the China-Pakistan economic corridor has also become a model for global cooperation for the benefit of the people. A society's ability to disseminate and diffuse information would be severely limited without publishing books. Knowledge transmission is an integral aspect of it. There is a strong need to introduce mainstream thinkers' works, increase publication investment, cultivate professional editors, enrich publication types, and expand cultural exchange styles. The study explores Chinese books translation work published in Pakistan National Language in Urdu. This article focuses on the translator's role as a cultural mediator who must faithfully communicate the intricacies of the literary material. The debate's heart is translating culturally unique things like proverbs, figurative language, references to religion, mythology, literature, and stylistics. Literary publishing on the web represents a new, era of creative expression and enhanced democratization of literary culture, and its impact on writers, readers, publishers, and libraries has been significant. The study revealed that in sufficiencies such as lack of introduction, the low conversion rate of published works, and unstable publishing structure. We believe that it is necessary to encourage publishing cultural exchanges and strengthening the relationship between both countries.

Keywords: CPEC; Chinese Book; Libraries; Social media

Introduction

One of the world's largest economic platforms will be established by China under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Win-Win is a motto of mutual collaboration, respect, and a community of shared destiny that will bring the globe together (Gao, 2020: Asif & Ling, 2018). The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is one of the mega projects of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) that would deepen the connection between Pakistan and China, the relationship between China and Pakistan has been deepening, and the China Pakistan economic corridor, which is a landmark project of the "belt and road", has also reaped fruitful results (Asif & Ling, 2019). CPEC is a very unique form of cooperation throughout the world, all cooperation has conditions attached, and the cooperation of the China Pakistan economic corridor is based on the friendship between the two peoples and is a cooperation to ensure the interests of the two peoples. this is a very unique partnership. while also opening up new opportunities for Pakistan (Wolf, 2018: Asif, 2018). Mutual understanding between China and Pakistan will facilitate deeper cooperation with other countries in the region, provide a larger platform for the spread of Chinese culture in Pakistan and the rest of the world, deepen global understanding of China, and increase the international influence of Chinese culture. With the implementation of more collaboration in the CPEC and the pursuit of more desired demands for regional growth, it is an opportune moment for China and Pakistan to foster more and more profound cultural exchanges and cooperation between both countries (McCartney, 2021: Asif et al., 2021). The "Belt and Road" is a route for business and trade and a path for civilizations to communicate and learn from one another. National friendship is based on people's shared interests, and people's shared interests are based on their ability to communicate with one another. 'Belt and road' building rely heavily on interpersonal relationships. Foreigners writing in China plan will provide a new channel to link China with the ancient Silk Road nations, which will build the groundwork for developing cultural and publishing cooperation between the two countries. In 2017, a banner year for foreigner writing China program, as the secretariat shared collection guidelines for the "national silk road literature project" on a global scale, garnering positive responses from people from all walks of life at home and abroad. The secretariat sorted and summarized 92 topics from 85 institutions both at home and abroad and a large number of internationally renowned sinologists, writers, and other members who registered for the program. The content collected in the second issue includes topics such as Chinese philosophy, politics, economy, culture, literature, and art, and the book includes contributions from more than 120 international authors, including sinologists, translators, professors, political professionals, full-time writers, publishers, editors, doctors, journalists, and others in various fields. It includes 66 English language books, 8 German-language books, 1 French-language book, 3 Romanian language books, 7 Arabic language books, 2 Spanish language books, 1 Ukrainian language book, 1 Turkish language book, 2 Urdu language books, 1 Lao language book, and 1 Croatian language book. The books have been published in a total of 91 different categories (some of the works have multi-lingual publishing intentions); the creative themes covered by the books range from philosophy to politics to literature to biography to

film to travelogue to regional culture to international relations to cultural exchanges to current affairs and other categories. Traditional Chinese culture is brought to the attention of Pakistani youths via comic picture books, which has a significant impact on their knowledge of Chinese customs and the promotion of cultural exchanges between China and Pakistan (China culture network, 2018).

Since it enables the distribution and dispersion of knowledge, book publishing has played an essential part in the development of every civilization (Asif, Yang, Ali & Hashim, 2022). As part of a knowledge distribution system, it stores and distributes information. Increasing people-to-people contact via higher education exchange programs, cultural events, seminars, and interactive programs in the course of media should be prioritized by the governments of both nations in order for CPEC to be completed successfully. The Chinese Culture Translation and Research Network (from now on referred to as "CCTSS"), which aims to develop further the Chinese Culture Translation and Research Network's overseas sinologists, translators, and talents database, as well as to promote the implementation of cultural exchanges between China and Pakistan, was established on the occasion of the 70th anniversary of the establishment of diplomatic relations between China and Pakistan. The establishment of the CCTSS joint social science literature publishing company was intended to enhance the mutual translation and publication of works between the two nations while also deepening mutual understanding between the two peoples. In addition, the "China-Pakistan Translation Workshop" brings together well-known Chinese sinologists and translators in Pakistan, as well as Publishing Institutions in China and Pakistan, to collaborate on translating, publishing, and promoting excellent Chinese books suitable for Pakistan's national conditions and readers' reading habits. It also brings together Pakistan's local media resources to introduce Chinese works to Pakistani readers in a targeted manner (Wong & Fuehrer, 2016).

Culture

Defining the phrase 'culture' is a problematic and exhausting endeavor, just as the term and its components are, and there is no such thing as a 100 percent comprehensive and correct description for the term 'culture.' However, the following are various definitions of 'culture' by academicians. Collins English Dictionary and Thesaurus (2004) define culture as "civilization, conventions, lifestyle, mores, society, and way of life." According to another definition, culture is defined as follows: "a particular society's or group's religious beliefs, customs, art, or other forms of expression: a particular society with its own religious beliefs, ways of life, and other forms of expression: a particular way of thinking, behaving, or working that exists in a place or organization (such as a business)" (Lysgård, 2013). According to Peter Newmark's 'The Text Book of Translation' (1988), culture is defined as "the way of life and its expressions that are specific to a group that utilizes a certain language as its means of expression." According to him, culture is specific to a particular group of people and involves how they interact with one another and society. This encompasses customs, rituals, faiths, behaviors, and language, among

other things. However, the role of language as one of the characteristics of culture is crucial since it serves as the means of expression for the culture in question.

Awareness of culture in translation

Though there may be cultural references in most translation subfields except science translation, the connection between culture and translation can be seen and analyzed about Literary Translation, including novels, short stories, poetry, drama, classical prose, and poetry and biographies. On the other hand, a translator serves as a conduit for the characteristics and spirit of the Source Culture to the Target Culture. Finding the suitable method for that assignment is where he runs into trouble. As a result, the translator must bridge the gap between two unfamiliar cultures and provide a route for the Target Readers to comprehend and appreciate the Source Culture as much as the limits allow.

There are many civilizations in every corner of the earth. For example, European culture is vastly distinct from Asian culture, which is very different from African culture, and so on. When a translator is tasked with translating a work from European culture for African target readers, he must concentrate on not destroying the original text and expressing the concepts as accurately as possible. There may be instances of cultural shock. The translator's job is to reduce them as much as feasible. It includes nations and territories with diverse cultural backgrounds and political systems as part of the Belt and Road Initiative. Cultural exchanges play an essential part in the creation of the "belt and road," and the growth of connections between nations requires both the "hard" backing of economic and commercial cooperation as well as the "soft" support of exchanges of cultural ideas and practices. Culture is transmitted via literature, and reading great works is one of the most efficient methods to understand diverse civilizations. In order to carry out the spirit of the important initiative put forward by General Secretary Xi Jinping at the May 2019 Conference on Dialogue of Asian Civilizations, "China is willing to work with relevant countries to implement the plan for the mutual translation of classic works in Asia," after extensive preparations and consultations between relevant departments of China and Pakistan, the two countries announced the signing of a memorandum of understanding on January 5, 2021, which will be effective on January 1, 2022. Expressly, the two nations agreed to start the "China-Pakistan classics translation and publishing project" to assist the mutual translation and publication of classics and significant works from both countries, according to the memorandum. Within five years, China and Pakistan will fully realize their potential as publishing culture experts, and they will translate and publish 50 different types of classic works that are "the most classic, most important, and widely acclaimed" in both countries. These works will be dedicated to the readers of both countries.

The signing of the memorandum of understanding between China and Pakistan follows the joint announcement by the leaders of China and Singapore on December 8, 2020, on the signing of a memorandum of understanding on the mutual translation and publication of classic works between China and Singapore, as well as the signing of the first memorandum of understanding between China and Asian countries at the beginning of 2021, which adds color to the already vibrant

relationship between China and Asian countries. The signing of the memorandum of understanding between China and It is anticipated that the signing and implementation of the Memorandum of Understanding on the mutual translation and publication of classic works between China and Pakistan will provide a fresh

humanistic impetus to the joint construction of a community of common destiny between the two countries, as well as further consolidate the humanistic foundation for consolidating the all-weather friendship between the two countries, which will be beneficial for translating and introducing classic works. According to Sun, Pitafi, Ghani, & Islam (2020), The road is lengthy, but it is only a struggle if not forget your initial goal. As the "China Pakistan cultural corridor" continues to take shape, the two countries' cultures will work together to actively participate in the project of mutual translation and publication of classic works, building on the recent successes. The two countries' cultures will also work to be the first, cut through the thorns, and pioneer cultural exchanges between China and Pakistan.

The Importance of Cultural Sensitization in Translation

Translation is a well-known method of conveying ideas written in one language to another via a different language. The history of the translation process dates back to the early ages, and it may be divided into categories such as Asian translation history, European translation history, African translation history, and so on. It is discovered while researching the history of translation that the name 'Translation' (in English) derives from the Latin word 'translatio,' which literally translates as "a carrying over" or "a bringing across" (Chen, 2015; Lee, 2016). On the other hand, Translating requires two languages, such as the Source Language and the Target Language or the Destination Language, which must be communicated effectively. If it is not already clear, the language of the original text or the language from which you are translating is referred to as the Source Language (SL), and the language into which you are translating is referred to as the Target Language (TL) or the Destination Language, respectively. Keeping in mind that there might be several target languages, but only one source language is essential to keep in mind while translating. Translation, according to Eugene Nida, is defined as follows:

Transcribing S-1 communications into another language entails duplicating the closest natural equivalent of the S-1 messages, first in terms of meaning and then in terms of style (Nida & Taber, 1969). The process of translation is defined as the restoration of original work, in which the message in the Source Language is reproduced using the closest comparable equivalent in the target language. The message conveyed by the Source Text is given precedence in this instance. Then the value of the style, which is an integral component of the original, is emphasized. Also worth noting is Peter Newmark's definition, which states that "translation is a craft consisting of the endeavor to replace a written statement in one language with the identical message or statement in another language" (Newmark, 1981).

According to Newmark, this is a reinstatement. Priority is given to the delivered message. He refers to it as a 'craft' while appreciating its aesthetic significance. Additionally, Goethe writes that "translators are like active matchmakers who extol

the virtues of a half-veiled beauty: they inspire an insatiable longing for the original." Simultaneously, The Encyclopedia of Translation Studies, edited by Mona Baker, provides an in-depth examination of Translation Studies from various viewpoints. Given that this essay is about culture and translation, the following definition is critical. She refers to it as an 'intercultural dialogue process': "Translation is seen here largely as an intercultural communication process, the outcome of which is a text capable of operating effectively in a particular scenario and context of usage" (Baker & Mona 1998). However, one cannot assert that translation is a simple matter of two languages. It is always inclusive of both languages' people and culture. When a reader examines the original text and the translation, he or she may believe that the translation process is limited to languages, words, and grammar. Though they are physically unseen, it is essential to remember that the people and culture are inextricably linked to the material being translated.

Method of The Study

The overall aim of this study was to assess Chinese Translation work Published in Pakistan’s National Language (Urdu). Based on selected books, it is discovered mainly through current culture, awareness, and importance. A review of the literature was performed to identify how many books are translated into Urdu language and the purpose of the abundance of publications.

Search Strategy

A broad search strategy was developed to extract the maximum relevant literature. The researcher selected the three subject-specific databases Google, Pak-China Culture App on WeChat, China Daily News, Economic Daily. The following keywords were used to retrieve the data “CPEC” OR “Chinese Book” OR “Libraries” OR “Chinese Book” OR “Social Media”

Translated Books in Urdu

In 2021, the annual output edition and imported edition excellent book promotion activity jointly sponsored by the International Cooperation and Publishing Committee of the Publisher's Association of China, the China Press, and Publication Research Institute, and the Publishing Reference Magazine Agency announced the 20th output edition and imported edition of excellent books, of which "poverty reduction war: the battle against poverty (Urdu)" has been awarded the excellent output edition award and the excellent imported edition award.

Poverty is the common adversary of humanity, and it is an issue that all nations throughout the globe and the international community must confront. In pursuit of these values, humanity works tirelessly to promote progress, alleviate poverty, and achieve shared wealth worldwide. In this book, which was authorized by China Pictorial and published by the Pakistan-China Universal Publishing House, the war of poverty alleviation: the battle against poverty (in Urdu) illustrates China's achievements in rural poverty alleviation and development, as well as its contribution to humanity, through a wealth of text and images? At the National Poverty Alleviation Summary and Commendation Conference in 2021, General Secretary Xi Jinping gravely proclaimed that "China's poverty alleviation campaign has gained a sweeping triumph." This signifies that we have made historic and significant progress in resolving the problem of absolute poverty that has bedeviled the Chinese nation for thousands of years, and that has been contributed Chinese samples, Chinese wisdom, and Chinese strength to the cause of poverty reduction throughout the world." Poverty alleviation is not the end but rather the beginning of a new life, a new struggle. Even as the year 2021 draws to a close, the culture of China and Pakistan will not lose sight of its original purpose, but will instead continue to move forward, insist on telling Chinese stories well, spreading Chinese culture, and promoting cultural "going out" to a higher level, resulting in new achievements. Urdu edition of Chinese book promotion column - "China in action" series of books This issue of the Urdu edition of the Chinese book promotion column will introduce the Urdu edition of the "China in action" series "low-carbon new life," "eradication of poppies," "escort the Gulf of Aden," and "transnational rescue" by the China Pictorial News Agency authorized Pakistan-China universal publishing house "low-carbon new life," "eradication of poppies," "escort the Gulf of Aden," and "transnational rescue. Hebei University's research center for intercultural

communication and the research center of Hebei university collaborated to organize and assemble the Urdu version of the series of books produced and distributed in Islamabad, Pakistan's capital city. These books aim to better introduce China's practices in environmental protection, anti-drug control, maintaining the safety of international navigation, and providing international humanitarian assistance to the Pakistani people. They are masterpieces in terms of presenting China's image and spreading China's voice around the world.

Using specific words and pictures, as well as specific people and events, this book aims to comprehensively reflect "low-carbon China" by highlighting: government policies and initiatives; Chinese enterprises under the initiative of government; actively pursue the rational exploitation and full use of resources; participate in environmental protection work; reflect the specific stories of Chinese citizens; actively conserve energy and water, and promote environmental protection. We are actively engaged in developing a society that conserves resources and protects the environment

As a responsible large nation, China's self-confidence, tranquility, and bravery were shown in 2009 when the people's navy was sent to the Gulf of Aden and the seas off the coast of Somalia to accompany the country. While pirate activity was formerly

widespread and widely acknowledged as harmful, China's ability to keep peace has been shown in the region's maritime waters. The more than 50,000 ships that sail through this treacherous water every year have subsequently received an extra shoulder on which they may count to protect them from harm. China has successfully re-established itself as a powerful but responsible nation. Since the whole team of people participating in the preparation of this book is made up of shipboard journalists, they have access to exclusive, unique, and actual photos in addition to the Xinhua news agency press release photos, and some of these photos are being published here for the first time.

The Chinese rescue team has traveled to Algeria, Iran, Indonesia, Pakistan, and other countries seven times in the last seven years to carry out international humanitarian rescue operations, withstanding the severe test of significant disasters and bringing honor to their homeland and people, as well as bringing fame and glory to the Chinese army. Readers at home and abroad can gain a better understanding of the epitome of the Chinese hero group on the international rescue stage, their spirit of infinite loyalty to the motherland and people in the practice of medical rescue, their international humanitarian spirit of assisting the needy, and saving the lives of the injured, their fighting spirit of not fearing hardships and dangers, challenging the limits of life, and their professional spirit of dedication and excellence.

As a global public nuisance, the international community must control narcotics urgently and collectively. China has implemented several actions in recent years in response to the deteriorating anti-drug situation and has seen impressive achievements due to these efforts. As the world's most populous country, joining forces with the international community to perform an excellent job in its anti-drug campaign is a significant contribution to the globe. "Eradicating Poppies" is a narrative tale that uses a plethora of instances and particular characters and stories to explain the circumstances of China's collaboration with the world community and collaborative anti-drug cooperation in the form of visuals and prose.

Watching Spring has been published in Pakistan's Urdu language, and books from the country's national library have been placed on the shelves and made available for purchase. The Urdu edition of "watching spring," which was authorized by the Jiangxi Fine Arts Publishing House and published by the Pakistan-China Global Publishing House in April 2021, has been printed for the first time and is available in bookstores and schools throughout the country's capital and regions. The book's advertising campaign has been postponed until late September 2021 owing to the covid-19 epidemic. The Pakistan-China global publishing house, with support from the cultural department of the Chinese Embassy in Pakistan and the Chinese Cultural Center of Pakistan, and as the organizer of the Urdu edition of "watching spring," the Pakistan-China global publishing house co-organized by the national library of Pakistan, Ningxia Zhenna China-Pakistan cultural development co., Ltd., the cross-cultural communication research center of Hebei University, the northern university for nationalities. Promotional actions relating to the worldwide collaborative battle against the new crown pneumonia pandemic are undertaken. He hopes that in the future, Bazhong universal publishing house will translate more classic Chinese works, allowing batie to gain a better understanding of China. He also hopes that in the future, he will have more opportunities to collaborate with Jiangxi fine arts

publishing house, allowing us to reach out through culture and deepen our partnership with one another.

The Urdu version of "aiding the Hubei medical team" has been approved by the China Pictorial Publishing House and will be translated and published by the Pakistan-China Global Publishing House in 2021, with a publication date in Pakistan 2021. China Net authorized the compilation and creation of the first edition of the book (in English), and nearly 30 people, including xue lisheng and wang youcai, editors-in-chief of China pictorial, formed the "aid to Hubei medical team" compilation and creation team, which completed the project in only two weeks from project establishment to final edition, collecting images and videos taken by medical staff on the front lines of the epidemic in near-real-time. The images and videos were collected by medical staff on the. Because the epidemic came on so suddenly, many medical teams were assembled at random and sent to the front lines. Although their photographic abilities may need to be improved, the photographs and films they capture as first-hand materials serve to document and illustrate their genuine, remarkable experiences. This book was written to show the heroic achievements of medical personnel during times of crisis, detailing how they overcame obstacles and suffering to save countless lives. China Pictorial established the "aide medical team" editorial team based on these photographs and videos and published this book. The author strives to present a realistic and multifaceted picture of the epidemic's fight against the epidemic in this book.

From November 2012 to 2014, Xi Jinping delivered 79 speeches, talks, interviews, notes, and letters in "Xi Jinping: The Governance of China." This writing has been translated into 16 other languages and distributed more than 6.2 million copies throughout the globe. For the first time, the Urdu translation of the book will allow more Pakistanis to realize how important the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is to their country. "Most Pakistanis do not speak English; therefore, this book is a good resource for those who are interested in learning about the great things the Chinese government is doing. CPEC and China-Pakistan friendship are all the rage, but now they will understand the importance of the relationship between the two countries ", it is a. The CEO of Jamhoori Publications, who is in charge of translating the Urdu edition of the book, stated that translating a Chinese president's book in Urdu is an honor and a joy for him. You may learn about Chinese politics and the vision of President Xi Jinping by reading this book. China-Pakistan friendship plays a significant role in the region and the globe." Urdu is Pakistan's opinion-making language, and via Urdu publications, a commoner may readily comprehend China's position, leadership, and economic and political responsibilities (China Daily, 2017).

According to Li Yi, Chairman of Ningxia Zhenna China-Pakistan Cultural Development Co., Ltd., translating Chinese idiom tales into Pakistani is no easy process! We want to introduce ancient Chinese literature to Pakistan's schools and libraries so that more people may learn about the country's rich cultural heritage.

For example, when it comes to the Urdu version of the "Chinese classic traditional story animation series," Ningxia zhenna will select a translation graduate student who is studying Chinese at a local university in Pakistan to act as a translator in order to be authentic in the language and acceptability by the Pakistani audience, during the process of translating Chinese idiom stories into Urdu. The candidate must first pass the written and oral examinations, and then c Ningxia Zhenna conducts an interview using the translation that has been confirmed to pass the translation test. Classic Chinese idioms such as "flowing water in the mountains" and "ask without shame" made their way into Pakistan after 22 days of translation, editing, printing, and publishing. To Li Yi, "we have picked 30 great expressions to be translated into a book and an expression narrative, in a series of 30 volumes." To date, 100,000 copies have been produced, with part of them being given to primary and secondary schools and libraries across Pakistan.

"In the process of cultural dissemination, we are also excavating Pakistan’s local talent think tanks, using the resources of the China-Pakistan interconnection, not only to spread Chinese culture to Pakistan but also to bring Pakistan’s culture to China and promote cultural exchanges and cooperation between the two countries," said Li Yi. " He informed that he traveled to Pakistan to study in 2001 and worked very hard in Pakistan for 20 years after graduation. When Li Yi first arrived in Pakistan to study, he discovered that, when compared to western cultural literature, Chinese cultural classics may practically be regarded as "sporadic" in the country's libraries and shops. Li Yi founded Ningxia Zhenna China-Pakistan Cultural Development Co., Ltd. in 2013 to promote the dissemination of Sino-Pakistan culture. In 2017, he established Pakistan-China Global Culture Interconnection Co., Ltd. in Pakistan to promote business cooperation between China and Pakistan. Li Yi is a Chinese-born Pakistani businesswoman who lives in Beijing.

When asked about the company's plans for the future, li yi said, "In the future, we will pay more attention to translation and dubbing, and we will convey the Chinese voice and the Chinese tale in the video to Pakistan." The second "oriental love rhyme - Chinese traditional culture and creativity exhibition" will be held in Pakistan in April 2022, According to Li Yi, who also revealed that the first exhibition, which took place in 2019, will be followed by a second exhibition, which will take place after the epidemic in Pakistan has been eradicated.

'Retrograde' aspires to use the most detailed images and the most straightforward narrative to show children the genuine, warm, and transcendent anti-epidemic scenes of those obscure "warriors," demonstrating China's spirit in confronting the new crown pneumonia epidemic, growing in courage and determination as it goes up against the current. "Retrograde" can not only provide children with a new understanding of heroes, responsibilities, and dedication in reading, but it can also teach them about the excellent character of the Chinese people, who are willing to help one another and overcome difficulties. It can also help foreigners understand China's efforts and contributions in the fight against the epidemic in the first place. As a result, the external propagation of "retrograde" is of great importance, as it not only carries forward the Chinese spirit but also serves as a model for international anti-epidemic efforts. Since the disease outbreak, hundreds of medical professionals, police officers, couriers, and even regular citizens have devoted their lives to protecting the nation and its citizens. As the "most beautiful retrogrades," they give up their modest dwellings to care for everyone, and they devote their life to erecting a "love-line of protection" around us. According to the classic picture book, "what does a hero look like?" they are "regular individuals who have stepped forward to share their stories.

In this section, we will tell you about a picture book series called "Avanti classic story" made by Wang Hongbin, who is from Xinxiang and won the UNESCO Asia-pacific children's book illustration award. The series is based on the classic Avanti story and shows how the "eternal wise man" Avanti used Chinese people's wisdom to solve the problems of the wise men and greedy ric. Learn about the unique characteristics of products made in Xinxiang. Gain a sense of what life is like for people all over the world People in Pakistan's publishing company, Pakistan and China Global Publishing House, started a new series of Urdu books for the series in 2019.

Xinjiang Youth Publishing House published the "when I was a child" Chinese picture book series, written by the famous children's literature writer and picture book

course expert bao dongni. The series has a total of 4 books. The "when I was a child" Chinese picture book series won the following awards:

The General Administration of Press and Publication has suggested 100 types of good books to young people all around the nation, and they are divided into three categories. A tenth output edition and an imported edition have been released. Excellent book selection exercise (with an output board) includes award-winning literature. The third volume of "three hundred" unique and superb novels is now available. The most beautiful books on both sides of the Taiwan Straits are displayed at the innovative cross-strait urban design biennale. Participants in the assessment of external propaganda goods included representatives from the central propaganda department. The series was introduced in 2019 by Pakistan's Pakistan-China global publishing house in Urdu and has since been exported to Pakistan. It was nominated for the "4th China excellent publication nomination award" and the "China original animation book award." It was also nominated for the "2018 China original picture book 200" list.

The 15 books in the "Story China" picture book series!

The series was introduced in 2019 by Pakistan's Pakistan-China global publishing house in Urdu. Among the 15 books in the "story China" picture book series, the zodiac series includes "rain dragon," "flower rooster," "sheep girl," "white horse and god diagram," "little wukong," "Chinese celebrity series" "Confucius," "Genghis

khan," "Cangjie zaozi," "cai lun papermaking," "Famous Chinese places" series include "Shaolin temple," "great wall," "forbidden city," "terracotta warriors," "Dunhuang mogao grottoes," "story China" picture book series with the help of ink-drenched picture book form, with the help of the most beautiful Chinese stories, the artistic beauty of Chinese painting and the charm of traditional Chinese culture is vividly expressed. Now, the series has been translated into Urdu and published in Pakistan. The "story of China" picture book series will bring Pakistani children a unique Chinese culture reading experience. Some screenshots of the Urdu edition of the "story China" picture book series are below.

"Dorje" is a Chinese-Tibetan bilingual picture book based on a popular Tibetan children's musical called "Dorje." It is a book by East China Normal University Press. It came out in November 2018. Today, I want to show you the Urdu version of "Dorje" sent to Pakistan. Before you read the Urdu version of "Dorje," the editor will give you some background on the original version of the story. Dorje was published in Nepali, Arabic, and Urdu in 2020 in Pakistan, and it worked.

The Urdu version of "I want to know your name" is officially launched (2020)

This is a poem about ordinary heroes, and it's also a tribute to spring. It praises workers from all walks of life who have worked hard to fight the new crown pneumonia epidemic. This particular spring has made sure that Wuhan's fight against the "epidemic" will be a success thanks to their selfless dedication. The book talks about all the people who stayed in Wuhan to help fight the epidemic and came back to Wuhan after the epidemic was over. Medical workers, hospital builders, couriers, journalists, taxi drivers, and more. Poetry filled with affection shows how people on the front lines in the fight against the epidemic keep going and how much love they have for each other. He shows how the Chinese nation is strong enough to help each other and how they all care about each other and support each other. Picture book: "belt and road" China first goes to the Pakistan pen farming house school to spread more Chinese culture, let more suitable children's picture books come to Pakistan, and let Pakistani children see more good picture books. President of the China Pakistan culture group and Pakistan's representative to the global culture interconnection co., Ltd., dr. Li Yi visited the pengon house Rawalpindi branch to encourage students to learn more about Chinese culture and other fields and help Pakistan grow and prosper in the future. They also wanted to strengthen their friendship between the two countries.

Ningxia and zhenna are both in charge of the activity. The cultural development company, Pakistan China global culture interconnection co., Ltd., Hebei university cross-cultural communication research center, and several domestic publishing houses will launch the "belt and road" children's picture book into campus activities. This project aims to deliver China's best children's picture books to nearly 100 schools in Pakistan in the next few years so that Pakistani students can experience and learn from the books and cultures of China.

The road to culture - treasures of Chinese Culture the road to the pinnacle
 China's 40 years of success yuan Longping,
 The father of hybrid rice
 "Forever lei Feng spirit"

"Love blue sky yang liwei"

"The red handprint of xiaogang village"

"30 kinds of Chinese classic traditional stories and animation series"

The Pakistan Literary Institute recently held a news release of new books in Islamabad and introduced to Pakistan readers three book titles of Chinese literature translated and published by the Pakistan Literary Institute into Urdu. It is reported that this is the first time for Pakistan to publish Chinese literature in the Urdu language. The three titles of Chinese Literature in the Urdu language translated and published by the Pakistan Literary Institute are: " Saint Confucius," "The Collection of Chinese Ancient Poems," and "The Collection of Chinese Classical and Modern Literary Works." These three books were examples of Pakistani writers' contribution to the development of bilateral relations, but they also celebrated the 55th year of establishing diplomatic relations between China and Pakistan, PAL chief Iftikhar Arif told Business Recorder. Professor Aftab Shamim, who supervised the translation project of the three books, said the translation had been done using current words phraseology and the meaning of words. He said the last ambassador and Cultural Counsellor, Shang Bong Xia, students of Professor Shamim, have been very cooperative in the translation project.

The Seer of China: Reading Lu Xun in Urdu, In the Centenary Year of The CPC (2021)

2021 marks the centenary year of the foundation of the CPC, and it is here that a volume of translations in Urdu of Lu Xun’s selected stories feels welcome. While the work of Lu Xun has been translated and re-translated multiple times into English and other major languages, given his stature in Chinese letters, the same cannot be said of Urdu. However, unlike Tagore, Iqbal, and Premchand, Lu Xun could never be thoroughly canonized in modern China, which is as accurate of the 21st century as the last one, despite effusive praise from Mao Zedong. Instead, the ancient thinker Confucius was and continues to be championed far more by the Chinese revolutionary state. Over here in Pakistan, with its much-vaunted history of China-Pakistan relations, we have never familiarized ourselves with any significant elements of Chinese culture and literature – except a very rudimentary familiarity with the Chinese language, what with the multiplicity of Confucius Institutes opening up all over the world.

Libraries and their role

In modern societies, all things people do are organized by groups called institutions. Everyone who does a big job in the world, from economic performance to healthcare to education or research to business or industry, has it set up so that it can be done. Today, institutions and organizations are almost always in charge of protecting the environment or protecting people (Krolak,2006). When it comes to preserving and sharing the written word's wealth of knowledge, nothing compares to the work of libraries and other organizations of a similar kind. Libraries and other organizations that collect and manage knowledge and information are priceless, given how critical they are to human evolution as a whole. Libraries have a vital role in education,

research, and development, as well as in cultural activities, spiritual and ideological worlds, amusement, and enjoyment. Thanks to the rapid advancement of information technology and the widening range of user groups and their differing informational demands, knowledge, and information are becoming the driving force and direction of change in today's contemporary society. It needs to understand these concepts to appreciate the importance of libraries. As a result, you will better understand how professionals do their jobs.

Through their collections of books, Libraries serve as information and knowledge reservoirs. Having access to accurate information is essential for every human endeavor to advance society. Everyone from the researcher to the teacher to the student to the administrator to the industrial and business manager to the artisan to the entrepreneur to the farmer to the worker in the factory and on the farm requires information to better equip themselves for the fruitful pursuit of their respective vocations. The primary informational function of the library is to gather material holding information by using proper techniques of collection (Soroya & Ameen, 2016).

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Role of social media

Using social media, individuals may connect with others who have similar personal or professional interests, hobbies, backgrounds, or real-life connections. Social media is an online platform that people can create social networks or social relationships with other people. When it comes to young people, the influence of social media is tremendous. As time goes on, it becomes more evident that social media platforms have become an integral part of people's daily lives. Adolescents increasingly utilize their laptops, tablet computers, and smartphones to keep up with the latest Tweets and Facebook status updates from their peers and family members. As a result of technological advancements, individuals are being pushed to adopt various lifestyle choices. Young individuals may benefit from using social networking sites to help them become more socially adept. Social media is a kind of data communication on the internet. Conversations may take place on social media platforms as well information can be shared, and online content can be created. Blogs, microblogs, wikis, social networking sites, photo-sharing sites, instant messaging, video-sharing sites, podcasts, widgets, virtual worlds, and other kinds of social media are just a few examples of the many types of social media. Hundreds of millions of individuals across the globe use social media to exchange knowledge and build new relationships with one another (Ahmed, Sharif, Ihaddadene & Djeraba, 2008).

The phenomenon of social media growth has influenced a wide range of companies and sectors, including the publishing industry (Criswell & Canty, 2014). The use of social media has become an effective marketing strategy for publishers and merchants in today's digitally social era and has grown more popular. According to Kaplan and Haenlein, social media is "a collection of Internet-based apps that are built on the conceptual and technical underpinnings of Web 2.0 and that enable the production and sharing of User Generated Content." Publishers and book retailers may utilize social media to attract local and foreign readers, expanding their market presence internationally and increasing their revenue. To put it simply, such a platform enables publishers and merchants to network with consumers, simplify transactions, create revenue, offer services and support, and strengthen brand equity and customer relationships. The astonishing expansion of social media has shown its ability to impact the publishing sector. Social media has grown in importance as a marketing tool for publishers and bookstores, and it is also becoming more popular with buyers and readers alike. Customer opinion on social

media is also positive in the post-purchase stage since it allows them to share their thoughts and experiences.

In order to promote and sell Chinese translations of literary works, several social media strategies are used. One of the most effective promoting a book online is to establish a Facebook group centered on the author's work. We may simply gather together persons who have a shared interest in the book's subject matter by starting a Facebook Group for the book's theme. Now, this does not necessarily imply the creation of a Group for the book itself, but we may certainly do so! It is a fantastic strategy for fiction writers, particularly those who produce series since it allows them to write more quickly. You may also form a group focused on the topic of the Chinese translation book, whether it is business, natural health, beautiful romance, or epic fantasy, among other things. These groups can attract more Pakistani fans, but we will need to provide material that is not immediately relevant to the book in question; it is more about developing the community than advertising a particular title. It is necessary to share articles and tales actively, hold author cover reveals, initiate discussions around the topic of the Chinese book, and participate in exciting dialogues with like-minded Pakistani readers and writers to keep the group's members interested. Apart from generating interest in the book, such activities also aid in networking, establishing relationships, and developing productive contacts with Pakistani people, all of which may lead to book sales in the future.

As a result, it is necessary to participate in other Facebook communities to develop these contacts. Additionally, there are several Facebook books groups where Pakistani readers actively participate in conversations and offer their ideas.

Role of Social media platform to improve Chinese Book literature in Pakistan

Create an Author Website; No amount of social media exposure can compensate for the lack of a well-designed website for a Chinese author. A personal author website is vital to tie together all author branding and social media efforts and offer you the most visibility possible. Alternatively, some writers opt to create a detailed website with an active blog covering a wide range of themes relating to Chinese book writing. These blogs might emphasize the genres or issues that the author writes about and provide the motivation for a future book in Chinese translation and their love as storytellers. Regular blogging will also aid in the engagement of Pakistani readers, bringing more people to the Chinese author's website and exposing them to their work in the process. Adding a section for subscribing to an author's newsletter or encouraging email signups will allow the author to communicate with his audience more frequently. People like feeling as if they have a personal connection with the author. In order to do this, we might include a comment area or contact form on the

author's website. Remember to thank readers for their input and opinions (provided that everyone is courteous and that the scenario is not a trolling one).

Create an Author Fan Club; Another effective method for promoting Chinese translated novels is establishing an author fan club on social media sites such as Facebook. Fans of the Chinese-translated book and the author will have a specialized community where they will feel more connected to the author and the book's author. With an author fan club, all members can interact and ask questions in a confidential environment. Many writers have had great success with this method for promoting their books and connecting with their followers on a more personal level.

Launch a Twitter Campaign; The use of Twitter to promote Chinese author books in Pakistan is a vital marketing tool, and when utilized successfully, it may assist Chinese writers in driving sales and reaching the top of the bestsellers lists in Pakistan. Here are a few pointers to keep in mind to receive the best possible outcomes from the author's Twitter campaign.

Keep the Book Title Short; Twitter is difficult to grasp since it only allows 140 characters to advertise a Chinese author's book. Short titles should be used because short titles are excellent for tweeting, so keep titles brief and snappy while using Twitter.

Create a Unique #Hashtag; A unique hashtag surrounding the book title may be a fantastic idea since it enables readers to indicate keywords or subjects inside the author's tweets and because it allows Pakistani people to generate tweets that help promote Chinese authors' books and spread the word even farther by using the hashtag. Especially in the case of picking a hashtag, it may be quite beneficial to use a shorter version of the author's book title so that it is easily identifiable and topical, thereby contributing to the creation of buzz about the author's book.

Decide on a Landing Page; The author must choose a landing page to which he will lead his followers to provide them with further information. It might be the author's website or a product page on a retail website such as Amazon, for example.

Identify a Series of Tweetable Quotes from Author Book; Choose a few concise, intelligent, and fascinating phrases that will make for engaging tweets to promote a Chinese author's book on social media. However, it should only send out one or no more than two promotional tweets every day. Avoid over-promotion in the remainder of the author's tweets, and instead connect with his or her audience about relevant issues such as fascinating news articles, writing tips and techniques, behind-the-scenes insights at author's work, and other areas of interest.

Get Bloggers to Promote Chinese Author's Book; Using book bloggers to promote a book may significantly boost its chances of success. Bloggers well-known in the book industry have tens of thousands of followers, and Chinese authors' books may acquire a considerable amount of publicity in Pakistan via their blogging presence. It

is possible to get significant momentum for Chinese authors' books by enlisting the help of famous book bloggers to write book reviews for them and then aggressively spreading those reviews on their social networking platforms, such as their Facebook page and Twitter account. Many writers have collaborated with well-known book bloggers to get a book review, and they have received a positive reaction. Some suggestions for making the most of blogging possibilities are as follows:

Create Shareable Content; If we want to advertise our book widely across all social media channels, we must provide a steady stream of new material to keep our friends and followers interested and engaged. The following are the most often used content methods by authors:

Photos; Visual marketing is more popular than ever, therefore attempt to include a large number of images into the text of a Chinese author's book to capture the attention of Pakistani readers. Using a picture of a book cover may also be a fantastic option since everyone enjoys a well-designed book cover, and it is a simple method to disseminate the branding of a Chinese author's book.

Reviews; As we all know; positive Amazon book reviews are critical in increasing the visibility of any new book. Distribute these reviews throughout all social media platforms to generate interest among the author's target audience. Make the same move with the author's Goodreads reviews to create more possibilities.

Video clips; As previously said, videos are a significant success with viewers on social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter. Creating brief video snippets, such as an author interview or an entertaining video that highlights behind-the-scenes footage from the book's production, among other things, is a good idea. In addition, we can generate video blog entries, book trailers, and a variety of other things.

Try Out Instagram; For authors, Instagram is an excellent venue for marketing their books. So many writers are using Instagram to ruin their book promotion campaigns effectively.

Create an Outstanding Profile; To get started, the author's profile bio must be nothing short of spectacular. Create a unique profile; Include a headshot photo and an informative bio that demonstrates the author's quality as a writer on the author's profile page. Also available in the profile bio area is a URL that directs followers to the author's book's website or a specific landing page for further information or to purchase directly from the author's website (Jackson, 2021).

Conclusion

In the 21st century, the world has become global, cultural barriers are breaking down, and the modern world's cultures seem to be hybrid. Every nation is striving hard to cope with the changing world. In this kind of scenario, the role of translation has pivotal importance. There is a dire need to translate various kinds of literature in

Pakistani multi-lingual and multi-cultural society. It is the only way to bridge the linguistic, social, cultural, and political gaps. It can, if used correctly, bring peoples of different origins closer to one another—literature exchanges under the Framework of China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Pakistan and China are all-weather strategic cooperation partners and iron brothers. Literature and writers occupy a central role in strengthening the friendship between Pakistan and China, laying the foundation for the Community of shared destiny between our two nations. Both countries are working on other memoranda of understanding book translation and establishing links between major Chinese publishers and Pakistani printing companies. The translation of Chinese Literature into the Urdu language would help people of both countries understand each other’s culture. Cultural works translation and publishing would be an efficient way for both countries to know each other better and deepen understanding to bring their people-to-people relations to new heights. Chinese Culture Translation and Studies Support (CCTSS) has paved the way for Pak-China Literary Corridor to bring two people closer by launching the Sino-Pakistan translation workshop.

To promote Chinese literature in any other country like Pakistan, both countries' governments may collaborate to bring famous literary works to where they want them to be. Governments can provide financial assistance and all sorts of sponsorships to translate famous works of Chinese authors, dramatists, and writers. After translation of the desired works, it can be published in different publishing houses under the government association or others. After the publication of the literature infrequently read languages or local languages, the works can be launched publicly in the presence of literary figures and other people who can further promote these novels/books through libraries and related media, etc., By related social media by creating channels of discussion about Chinese literature on YouTube, providing quotations from those works on Instagram pages and introduction to this art by giving introductory posts on Facebook, Twitter or other platforms. Maximum interest and awareness about Chinese classical novels will increase the number of people and help spread Chinese culture in Pakistan. Social media will play a vital role and removing all barriers related to people's unawareness and help solve the communication barriers. This finding suggests that there is a need to study further to identify the ways to enhance the method of classical Chinese novels in Pakistan. There is also a need for a more in-depth investigation of the relationship between individuals' attitudes toward the innovation of online literary publishing, the values, and perceptions of the larger literary community, and the tenure requirements that define the cultures of academic departments and institutions of higher learning. In order to better comprehend the relationship between print and online literary works, further research is required. They have a better grasp of how the different

groups of people who engage with an online literature search for and find such works and how the format in which a work of literature is presented could alter the reader's behavior and comprehension would also be beneficial. Many Scholars suggested that online publications are most significant to understanding the culture and playing a vital role like a bridge among different countries. Academically associated authors' concerns may be distinct and need more investigation, even if print over electronic material preference has been examined in other disciplines.

Recommendations for further study

- A comprehensive study should be conducted on the Impact of Chinese books on society.
- A comprehensive study about the attitude of the user regarding Chinese book reading.
- The impact of Chinese literature change on the operation of academic libraries should be conducted.
- A comprehensive study on the university level to promote and publish translated work on famous Chinese writers.

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Declaration of Ownership

This article is our original work.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest to declare in this article.

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